

IN-VITRO PERMEATION OF ANTIOXIDANT ANALOGS FOR DIABETIC VASCULAR DISEASE

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1 General Introduction

Oxidative stress damages lipids, protein, enzymes, carbohydrate and DNA that could lead to cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular disease and aging. Antioxidant neutralizes free radicals by donating one of their own electrons and stopping the chain reaction. Antioxidant themselves do not become free radicals by donating an electrons because they are stable in either form. The supposed mechanisms for prophylaxis may include enhanced enzymatic detoxification of harmful compounds and inhibition of their binding to cellular DNA [1]. Many of the benefits derived from intake of such diets may be the result of synergism between natural antioxidants and the better known vitamin antioxidants. Necessity and superiority of formulated antioxidants over dietary antioxidants is well described; however, the oral bioavailability issues remain unaddressed. The dietary antioxidant bioavailability is dependent on a number of factors like food processing, food deprivation, stability of the antioxidant, stabilizing effect of food matrix to restrain the release of lipophilic antioxidants, the isomeric form present in it especially in case of carotenoids and the conjugated form in which it is present apart from the physicochemical and biopharmaceutical properties of the active agent. The problems associated with diabetes are a risk factor for cardiovascular disease involves nephropathy and retinopathy complications resulting cardiovascular disease leading cause of death in the diabetic population [2, 3]. The diabetes control and complications needed alternative treatment strategies, many researchers demonstrate oxidative stress induced by hyperglycemia generation of free radicals leads to development and progression of diabetes [4]. Excess production of these free radicals results in vascular dysfunction, damage to cellular proteins, membrane lipids and nucleic acids. It clears that antioxidants might be an

effective strategy for reducing these problems. Therefore, for effective approach with new strategies the antioxidants should be implemented in the treatment of diabetes [5]. Transdermal drug delivery offers an alternative route for free radical scavenger administration by the help of chemical penetration enhancers [6]. Novel drug delivery systems (NDDS) have an enormous impact on medical technology, significantly improving the performance of drugs in terms of efficacy, safety and patient compliance. NDDS can greatly improve the delivery of drugs which are poorly bioavailable due to their unfavorable physicochemical or pharmacokinetic parameters.

The presented works have utilized homogenizer to produce β -Carotene nanoemulsion from biologically inspired biopolymer Hyaluronic acid (HA) and poly lactic acid (PLA) composite with active biomolecule (Beta-carotene) by the help of emulsifier (Tween20) with chemical permeation enhancer ((CPE) oleic acid). The traditional permeation experimental apparatus using Franz diffusion cells provides a reliable in vitro technique for estimating the permeation of drugs through the membrane.

2. Experimental

2.1 Preparation of nanoemulsion

2.1.1. β -Carotene loaded HA nanoemulsion

Polymeric nanoemulsion was prepared by a modified double emulsion technique [7]. Each batch process is described as follows. At first, 30mL of double-distilled water containing Hyaluronic acid (natural, non-toxic, polysaccharide) (15mg) was emulsified with β -Carotene (5mg) and 5% oleic acid (chemical penetration enhancers) containing 3mL of acetone by using a high-speed homogenization to form primary emulsion. Next, 5mL of an aqueous

phase containing tween 20 (0.194g) was immediately poured into this primary emulsion then sonicated for 5 minute by using a probe sonicator at 40% amplitude then the emulsion was diluted by adding continuous phase. Acetone was then evaporated off and aqueous phase concentrated by using rotary evaporation technique this evaporation under reduce pressure (40°C) to final concentration of emulsion and named as F 1-W-OA (Formulation 1 with oleic acid).

2.1.2. β -Carotene loaded PLA nanoemulsion

For the synthesis of β -Carotene loaded PLA nanoemulsion, organic phase consist of β -Carotene (5mg) and natural, non-toxic, polysaccharide PLA (50mg) containing acetone (3ml) was added drop by drop in to the aqueous phase, which consist of emulsifier tween 20 (0.194g) with 5% oleic acid and emulsified with a help of high-speed homogenization to form primary emulsion. Then the procedure was followed similar to β -Carotene loaded HA nanoemulsion and named as F 2-W-OA (Formulation 2 with oleic acid).

2.2.1. Scanning electron microscopy

The shape and surface morphology of the β -Carotene loaded nanoparticle were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were mounted on double side adhesive carbon tapes in the metal stubs. Then the samples were coated with platinum at 120sec under vacuum and examine for their morphology at 15kV.

2.3. Drug entrapment efficiency

The entrapment efficiency of β -Carotene loaded nanoemulsion was determined as described below [8]. Nanoparticle was separated from the medium by ultracentrifugation at 15000rpm for 30 min. The amount of drug present in the nanoparticle was determined as the difference between the total amount of drug used to prepare the nanoemulsion and the amount of drug present in the medium. The supernatant was analyzed for drug entrapment. The amount of drug present in the supernatant was analyzed by using UV/Vis spectrophotometer. The spectrum wavelength was chosen as 450 nm for quantitative chemical analysis. The standard calibration curve was described by developing different concentration of β -Carotene (50–400 μ g) vs peak area. The drug entrapment was measured using

UV/Vis spectrophotometer. The percentage drug entrapment was determined using following equations.

$$\text{Nanoparticle recovery (\%)} = \frac{\text{Mass of nanoparticle recovered}}{\text{Mass of polymer particle drug and excipients used in formulation}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Drug content (\%, W/W)} = \frac{\text{Mass of drug in nanoparticle}}{\text{Mass of nanoparticle recovered}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Drug entrapment (\%)} = \frac{\text{Mass of drug in nanoparticle}}{\text{Mass of drug used in nanoparticle formulation}} \times 100$$

All the synthesis procedure was repeated three times to establish the reproducibility of nanoparticle synthesis.

2.4. Drug release profile

In vitro release of nanomedicine formulations was performed by using Franz diffusion cells [9]. The donor and the receiver chambers were 1 and 5mL, respectively. The receiver chamber temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ using a flow loop consisting of a water bath reservoir. The receiver chambers of the Franz diffusion cells were filled with PBS and stirred continuously using a magnetic stir bar. Egg shell membrane was placed between the donor and receiver chambers with the stratum corneum facing the donor chamber. Then, 1.0mL emulsions were placed inside the donor chambers of Franz diffusion cells. At different time intervals samples were withdrawn from the receiver chamber using a syringe. Fresh PBS was replaced in the receiver chambers. The collected samples were stored at 4°C until further analysis. The quantitative analysis validated using UV/Vis spectrophotometer. And To investigate the mathematical mechanism of drug releases from the pharmaceutical formulations were analyzed by the following kinetic equations: zero order, first order and Higuchi theoretical model [10].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Development of nanoemulsion

The nanoemulsions were synthesized by modified double emulsion technique. It was developed from two different natural polymers, named as F 1-W-OA and F 2-W-OA. This procedure is very easy than other conventional methods. β -Carotene with all

excipients was added in to acetone to forms organic phase. The organic phase containing mixture was added dropwise in to the aqueous phase containing mixture under vigorous stirring, it leads to get a crude emulsion followed by homogenization and sonication to make a uniform nanoemulsion.

3.2. Entrapment efficiency

The linearity range of standardization curve was found to be the correlation coefficient was 0.999 (Fig.1). The peak area of supernatants of drug loaded polymeric-particles was analyzed and used for β -Carotene quantification. The percentage drug content (drug loading) and drug entrapment was determined respectively by using the equations. The table 1 elicited the percentage of drug content and drug entrapment and recovery for the formulations. All the values represent the mean of triplicate determinations were reported for establishing the reproducibility of nanoemulsion synthesis.

3.3. Characterization of Drug loaded nanoparticles

In the present examination, β -Carotene nanoparticles were developed by two different phase polymeric methods which is aqueous soluble and organic soluble polymer. After concentrating the all the formulations were measured by SEM. The mean diameter of particles and β -Carotene loaded particles were observed under scanning electron microscope. Photographs of SEM (Fig.2) are obviously demonstrating the variation in particle size according to the formulation methods. In addition, the size of the nanoparticles produced from F 1-W-OA (190 nm) was smaller than F 2-W-OA (210nm). But the size of β -Carotene nanoparticle considerably closer to both formulations produced. Morphological characterization of nanoparticle by SEM showed a randomized distribution of semi-spheroid particles with different particle sizes and no aggregation were found. The larger surface area particles are more chance to aggregate. Inorder to overcome the aggregations needs to add a suitable surfactant in the formulations was necessary. Tween 20 appeared to be the most suitable surfactant in reducing aggregation between small particles [11]. From the photographs it is observed that the smooth surface with minimum diameters particle shows in the F 1-W-OA followed by F 2-W-OA.

3.4. In-vitro release study and release kinetics

Amount of released β -Carotene was quantified using UV analysis with the help of calibration curve. β -Carotene, a lipophilic drug, was successfully encapsulated on PLA nanoparticle using solvent evaporation method with high encapsulation efficiency drug loading. Antioxidant activity assay revealed that the functional activity of β -Carotene was retained after encapsulation. The in-vitro release setup of β -Carotene from nanoemulsion is shown in fig.3. In the present release study was observed that the F 1-W-OA shows maximum drug release rate compared to F 2-W-OA (Fig.4). F 1-W-OA shows highest percentage of drug release profile then F 2-W-OA (73.44 and 63.2 respectively). The detailed description of release profiles by a mathematical model function has been tried successfully employing different kinetics (zero order, first order and Higuchi square-root model) to achieve the mechanism of release [10]. egg shell membrane confirmed that β -Carotene was released from the formulations and thus could possibly diffuse by the human skin. The in-vitro drug release profile was calculated from the linear regression coefficient (R^2) were determined and presented in table -2. The release profile slowed sustained release time dependant diffusion erosion mechanism. High encapsulation efficiency of β -Carotene, and slow release makes the drugs loaded hyaluronic acid/PLA nanoemulsion a suitable candidate for the further development of nanomedicines. Further work of cytotoxicity, intra and extra cellular mechanisms, glutathione reductase regenerates mechanisms. This evidence levels, an indirect measurement of free-radical production that has been shown to be consistently elevated in diabetes. These investigations has to be continued with our lab and we aimed at preventing the generation of these reactive species as well as scavenging may prove more beneficial for clinical.

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Table.1. Percentage of nanoparticle recovery, drug content, entrapment and wastage for both formulations.

β -Carotene loaded nanoemulsion	Nanoparticle recovery (%)	Drug content (% W/W)	Drug entrapment (%)	Drug wastage (%)
F 1-W-OA	92.12±.01	2.57±.08	86.64±.16	13.36±.16
F 2-W-OA	85.43±.05	2.51±.27	78.4±.19	21.6±.08

Table.2. Release kinetics data of β -Carotene loaded polymeric nanoparticle

β -Carotene loaded nanoemulsion	Zero order	First order	Higuchi
F 1-W-OA	0.981	0.958	0.975
F 2-W-OA	0.953	0.981	0.980

Fig.1. Calibration curve of β -Carotene yielded by validated UV-visible spectroscopic methods. This was found by plotting various concentration of β -Carotene (mcg) vs. corresponding peak area.

Fig.2. SEM images of drug loaded nanoemulsion: (a) F 1-W-OA (190nm), (b) F 2-W-OA (210nm)

Fig.4. Release profile of β -Carotene from nanoemulsion using egg shell membrane. Release curve was obtained by plotting % of drug released vs. regular time intervals recorded in UV- visible spectroscopy, mean \pm S.D (n=3) are presented.

Fig.3. Drug release studies setup using Franz diffusion cells